

Scientific collaboration networks in the interdisciplinary field of biodiversity in central Germany

Aliakbar Akbaritabar¹

¹akbaritabar@demogr.mpg.de; akbaritabar@gmail.com

Max Planck Institute for Demographic Research, Rostock, (Germany)

German Centre for Higher Education Research and Science Studies, Berlin, (Germany)

Abstract

Examining the effectiveness of institutional scientific coalitions informs future policies. Since 1995, three universities in a central region in Germany have formed a coalition which later established an interdisciplinary centre. We consider the structure of scientific collaborations between coalition members, and the new centre within their regional context. We investigate the coalition's impact on the region's structure of collaborations with a specific focus on the field of biodiversity. Using publications data from 1996-2018 and co-authorship networks, we identify the most cohesive communities in the region and compare them with the scientific outcome of the coalition and new centre. Our results show that the newly established interdisciplinary centre has extensively bridged the member institutions. Yet, we identified more unrealized potential in the region. The level of interdisciplinary collaboration the coalition achieved could inform policymakers regarding other regions' and fields' scientific development plans. Nevertheless, geographical proximity, collaboration policies, funding, and organizational structure alone would not ensure a comprehensive scientific collaboration structure such as the one that the coalition aimed to construct.

Keywords: Internationalization; Co-authorship Network Analysis; Bipartite Community Detection; Universitätsbund Halle Jena Leipzig; German Centre for Integrative Biodiversity Research (iDiv)

Introduction

It is argued that scientific and complex economic activities are concentrated in urban and metropolitan areas (Balland et al., 2020). This concentration might be the result of a selective process of spatial proximity between knowledge-producing and -demanding institutions (Rammer et al., 2020). In specific cases and within a densely populated metropolitan region, remnants of a historical divide might put distance between institutions (Abbasiharofteh & Broekel, 2020).

This concentration of scientific activities in metropolitan and urban areas could motivate strategic coalitions between scientific institutions (e.g. academic and non-academic organizations). Akbaritabar (2021) showed that *geographical proximity* and being located in a densely populated metropolitan area, i.e. Berlin, was not enough for institutional collaboration ties to form. A history of division and competition on the one hand, and coalitions and policies to foster regional cooperation on the other hand, can lead to a complex scientific landscape and structure of scientific collaborations. This complexity is further exacerbated in combination with institutions' effort to maintain a unique identity and mutually exclusive scientific focus from their neighbouring institutions, while fostering close collaboration ties with them.

Specific disciplines have higher or lower internationalization of scientific collaborations. They have varying degrees of interdisciplinary focus which changes over time (Craven et al., 2019). These disciplines might have a global division of labour in that some researchers located in specific geographical areas focus on some themes or carry out only parts of the research work (e.g. data gathering and field work (Boshoff, 2009)). Hence the reason the literature calls for a more equal footing and benefit from scientific collaborations (Habel et al., 2014)). Biodiversity is one of these disciplines and previous research has shown a high degree of geographical specialization in this discipline. However, there might be an imbalance between the human

resources and funding sources on the one hand versus where the biodiversity of natural environment exists on the other hand, leading to researchers from Europe and North America being the main producers of the knowledge about other geographical areas mainly located in the global south (Haelewaters et al., 2021; Tydecks et al., 2018).

Studying structure of scientific collaborations in different contexts can reveal potential reasons behind strategic coalitions, if present. There might be field, national, or continental specificities playing a role in determining which institutions collaborate. Similarly, Shrum et al. (2007, 2001; Chompalov et al., 2002) studied *structures of scientific collaborations* in multi-organizational research projects and provided a typology of collaborations using *bureaucracy*¹ and *technology*² as two main concepts: bureaucratic (with a formalized structure and clear regulation of the decision-making process mostly in larger collaborations), leaderless (similar to bureaucratic but with multiple leaders), non-specialized (semi-bureaucratic with lower levels of formalization) and participatory (a democratic structure of decision making and collaboration). Even bureaucratic and semi-bureaucratic collaborations limited the scope of formal procedures to give members autonomy in production of scientific results.

We focus on a geographical area in central Germany consisting of the three cities of Halle (Saale), Jena, and Leipzig (i.e., HJL cities herein) and the field of biodiversity. These cities have a total population of 843,790 (about 25% of Berlin)³. We selected these three cities because since 1995, the three universities located there have maintained a formal agreement to foster interdisciplinary collaborations and formed a coalition named *Unibund*⁴. In addition, from 2012 this coalition, in collaboration with eight other non-university research institutions, has established an interdisciplinary centre, i.e., German Centre for Integrative Biodiversity Research (iDiv)⁵ (see Table 1 for the list of members). iDiv received two funding phases from the German Science Foundation (DFG)⁶ for 2012 till 2016 and 2016 till 2020. We analyse this strategic coalition as a natural experiment that has lasted 25 years and created a new organizational form, iDiv. We aimed to investigate the coalition's effect in shaping the structure of scientific collaborations in this region and among its members in the field of biodiversity and compare it with other fields of science in the region.

We take the structure of collaborations as represented by the coalition members on their website as the exhaustive repository of their scientific output. This selection is informed by a discussion with centre's members in December 2019. We compare this scientific output with the structure that we constructed based on the empirical data on scientific output of all institutions in the region. This way, we compare the coalition's scientific output with that of its regional context. This is an interesting region as it does not comply with the idea of a centralized and concentrated metropolitan area (see Figure 1) such as Berlin (Abbasiharofteh & Broekel, 2020; Akbaritabar, 2021) or other major cities (Balland et al., 2020). We explore how this top-down coalition is positioned in the scientific landscape of the region and structure of institutional collaborations.

¹A formalized hierarchical structure with defined division of labour, goals and means to achieve them.

²Scientific endeavour in the studied fields is highly dependent on complex technology to gather information and produce scientific results.

³Population counts from: <https://worldpopulationreview.com/countries/cities/germany> accessed on October 8th 2020.

⁴Universitätsbund Halle Jena Leipzig, <https://mitteldeutscher-unibund.de/ueber-uns/> accessed on October 8th 2020.

⁵Deutsches Zentrum für integrative Biodiversitätsforschung (iDiv) Halle-Jena-Leipzig, <https://www.idiv.de/en/about-idiv.html> accessed on October 8th 2020.

⁶Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft, DFG.

Figure 1: Approximate location of Halle, Jena, and Leipzig (HJL) cities and region in central Germany

Table 1 presents the list of Unibund and iDiv members. There were three universities (i.e. Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg, Friedrich Schiller University Jena, and Leipzig University) that from July 1995 formed Unibund and in collaboration with Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research (UFZ), they established iDiv in 2012 and seven other institutions joined them in this interdisciplinary network.

Table 1: Membership of institutions in Unibund and/or iDiv (Y = yes).

Institution	Unibund member?	iDiv Member?
1. Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg ⁷	Y	Y
2. Friedrich Schiller University Jena ⁸	Y	Y
3. Leipzig University ⁹	Y	Y
4. Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research – UFZ ¹⁰		Y
5. Max Planck Institute for Biogeochemistry (MPI BGC) ¹¹		Y
6. Max Planck Institute for Chemical Ecology (MPI CE) ¹²		Y
7. Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Anthropology ¹³		Y

⁷<https://ror.org/05gqaka33>

⁸<https://ror.org/05qpz1x62>

⁹<https://ror.org/03s7gtk40>

¹⁰<https://ror.org/000h6jb29>

¹¹<https://ror.org/051yxp643>

¹²<https://ror.org/02ks53214>

¹³<https://ror.org/02a33b393>

Institution	Unibund member?	iDiv Member?
8. Leibniz Institute German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures (DSMZ) ¹⁴		Y
9. Leibniz Institute of Plant Biochemistry (IPB) ¹⁵		Y
10. Leibniz Institute of Plant Genetics and Crop Plant Research (IPK) ¹⁶		Y
11. Leibniz Institute Senckenberg Museum of Natural History (SMNG) ¹⁷		Y

iDiv is the youngest among seven research centres currently funded by the DFG. The goal of the DFG's first funding phase (2012-2016) was to establish the centre to facilitate cooperation in later stages e.g. in the second funding phase (2016-2020). This is the first time the DFG has funded a research centre developed by a consortium of three universities and eight non-university research institutions, particularly as the institutions are located in three different federal states. iDiv is a disciplinary integration of biology, chemistry, physics, geosciences, economics, social sciences and computer sciences. The biodiversity field is known to be highly interdisciplinary (Craven et al., 2019; Tydecks et al., 2018), nevertheless, the main focus of iDiv is in natural sciences. iDiv has four main research areas: 1) biodiversity patterns, 2) biodiversity processes, 3) biodiversity functions, and 4) biodiversity and society. iDiv has obtained support from the local government bodies and from 2012 Saxony (Freistaat Sachsen) provided 2,600 m² space for the buildings and offices in Leipziger BioCity. Thuringia and Saxony-Anhalt (Thüringen und Sachsen-Anhalt) have four professorship chairs for this cooperation. iDiv's website¹⁸ states having 350 employees from 30 different nations.

Based on this introduction and background, we explore the interplay between different contextual variables and geographical proximity to investigate the structure of scientific collaborations in the HJL region¹⁹. We specifically focus on the Unibund and iDiv to identify how these strategic coalitions are positioned in the structure of the region's scientific collaborations. Therefore, after presenting the effect of *disambiguation* of scientific organizations' names on the structure of scientific collaborations as our main methodological contribution, we formulate and investigate the following macro, quantitative, and exploratory research questions:

- **RQ1:** How *collaborative* and *internationalized* is the scientific landscape of the HJL region?
- **RQ2:** Are there *field* differences in the rate of collaborative and internationalized scientific work?
- **RQ3:** Are there specific field, sectoral, national or continental *cohesive subgroups* driving the scientific collaborations in the HJL region?
- **RQ4:** Can we find evidence of Unibund's effect as a strategic coalition on the structure of scientific collaborations in the HJL region?
- **RQ5:** Can we find evidence of iDiv's effect as a new organizational form on the structure of scientific collaborations in the HJL region?

¹⁴<https://ror.org/02tyer376>

¹⁵<https://ror.org/01mzk5576>

¹⁶<https://ror.org/02skbsp27>

¹⁷<https://ror.org/05jv9s411>

¹⁸<https://www.idiv.de/en/about-idiv.html> accessed on October 8th 2020

¹⁹Or alternatively called HJL cities in following pages

The contributions of this paper are threefold: 1) We focus on the scientific output of the HJL region, present the share of collaborative works, and identify the share of international collaborations. We differentiate HJL region, Berlin, Germany, Europe and continental regions worldwide to investigate possible groupings. We examine the impact of the institutional scientific coalition in HJL region. To do so, we compare Unibund and iDiv's self-represented scientific output and institutional collaboration structure with the structure constructed from the empirical data on the larger context of HJL region. 2) We compare all OECD²⁰ scientific fields on the structure of collaborations and we include a sectoral view based on the type of organization involved in the collaborations. 3) We present the effect of the organization name disambiguation on results and employ a bipartite network modeling and bipartite community detection approach and present how it can be useful in the identification of denser collaborative structures.

We present our data source and modeling strategy in the Data and methods section, and summarize our main findings in the Results section, followed by the Discussion and conclusions section.

Data and methods

We used two publication datasets. First, to delineate all scientific output of the iDiv, we used all publications listed on their website (i.e., "iDiv" for brevity)²¹. We found a total of 2,583 records (including 18 code, 66 data, 2,393 DOI, and 106 PDF). We excluded those without or with problematic DOIs and searched the remaining records (2,371 unique DOIs) in Scopus 2019 from the German Bibliometrics Competence Centre (KB)²². The KB database was updated until April 2019, thus it did not include all publications from 2019 and 2020. Therefore, we extracted matching records up to the end of 2018 (1,749 unique records, 74%).

Second, in parallel, to use as a baseline for comparison, we extracted all *article*, *review* and *conference proceedings* documents published from the beginning of the Scopus database in 1996 until the end of 2018 with at least one authoring organization from *Halle* (or *Saale*), *Jena* or *Leipzig* (i.e., "HJL cities" for brevity). Our purpose here was to find both publications from *iDiv* and its predecessor, *Unibund*, and compare how the former coalition and its established interdisciplinary centre are positioned in the larger structure of scientific collaborations in the region.

In both datasets (i.e., *iDiv* and *HJL cities*), we included organizations worldwide who have collaborated with at least one Unibund or iDiv member. Our level of analysis was *scientific organization* (i.e., each academic or non-academic affiliation mentioned in a publication).

The data included meta-data for each publication such as *publication year*, *title*, *affiliation addresses*, *scientific field*, *journal name* and *document type*. We used a mapping of publications to OECD scientific fields based on Scopus ASJC²³ that reduces the number of subject categories from 33 to six (OECD, 2007). We compared the aggregate data of iDiv web and HJL cities with trends of different OECD scientific fields i.e., *Agricultural Sciences* (AS), *Engineering Technology* (ET), *Natural Sciences* (NS), *Medical and Health Sciences* (MHS), *Humanities* (H) and *Social Sciences* (SS). As some publications are assigned to multiple fields, in the aggregate analysis, we used the first assignment of each publication, but in a single field view, we take all

²⁰Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development

²¹<https://www.idiv.de/en/research/publications.html> (accessed on July 30th 2020)

²²Kompetenzzentrum Bibliometrie (KB), <http://bibliometrie.info>

²³All Science Journal Classification

publications with any class assignment in the given field, thus, interdisciplinary publications are covered separately in all their assigned fields.

We used the complete string of affiliation addresses to disambiguate institutions names and obtain further information (i.e., country, geographical coordinates (longitude and latitude) of the main address and type of organization as *education*, *non-profit*²⁴, *company*, *government*, *health-care*, *facility*²⁵, *archive*²⁶ and other, see Global Research Identifier Database (GRID) policies²⁷) from the Research Organization Registry (ROR) API²⁸. ROR aggregates data from GRID, ISNI²⁹, Crossref and Wikidata³⁰. We used the ROR snapshot from November 7th 2019. This disambiguation method takes into account different name spellings, including misspellings, acronyms, and multiple languages similar to methodology used by Akbaritabar (2021). It is important to note that in disambiguated versions of the data presented in the results section, we include only publications for which all contributing organizations are disambiguated and exclude those publications with one or more non-disambiguated co-authoring organizations. This reduces our coverage of publications, but has more reliable results. Because non-disambiguated data can lead to multiple representation of similar organizations in the structure.

We evaluated the quality of ROR disambiguation results by choosing a random sample of 100 organizations. A research assistant searched online for the organization names from Scopus and the disambiguated name from ROR to find the original address and confronted the two names to determine whether the match was reliable. The results indicated that in only 4% of the cases a false match was assigned and 96% of cases were reliable matches.

We constructed bipartite co-authorship networks (Breiger, 1974) using ties between publications and organizations (Katz & Martin, 1997). A one-mode projection of the co-authorship network is usually used in the literature (Akbaritabar et al., 2020). The problem with this projection is twofold. First, different structures in two-mode networks are projected to the same one-mode structure. It causes information about the underlying structure to be lost. Second, the one-mode projection can present an artificially higher connectivity due to publications with high number of authors that project to maximally connected cliques. Using methods for *bipartite networks* enable us to resolve the shortcomings (Akbaritabar & Barbato, 2021). However, these methods are still scarce and under development.

We extracted the largest connected component of the co-authorship network, i.e. the giant component, and investigated it to identify possible geographical, field and/or sector-based coalitions. Our aim was to see if there are cohesive subgroups of organizations preferentially collaborating *among* themselves. We investigated the potential underlying factors behind these groupings.

²⁴Organization that uses its surplus revenue to achieve its goals. Includes charities and other non-government research funding bodies. Example, the Max Planck Society itself (grid.4372.2)

²⁵A building or facility dedicated to research of a specific area, usually contains specialized equipment. Includes telescopes, observatories and particle accelerators. Example: child institutes of the Max Planck Society (e.g., Max Planck Institute for Demographic Research, grid.419511.9)

²⁶Repository of documents, artifacts, or specimens. Includes libraries and museums that are not part of a university. Example, New York Public Library (grid.429888.7)

²⁷<https://www.grid.ac/pages/policies>

²⁸<https://ror.org/about>

²⁹International Standard Name Identifier, <https://isni.org/>

³⁰<https://www.wikidata.org>

To identify communities of co-authorship, we used *bipartite community detection* by *Constant Potts model* (CPM). CPM is a specific version of Potts model (Reichardt & Bornholdt, 2004) proposed by Traag et al. (2011) as a *resolution-limit-free* method. It resolves the resolution limit problem in modularity (Newman, 2004) which can obstruct detection of small communities in large networks (Traag et al., 2019). We use the implementation in the *Leidenalg*³¹ library in Python (Akbaritabar, 2021; Akbaritabar & Barbato, 2021). Community detection emphasizes the importance of links *within* communities rather than those *between* them. CPM uses a resolution parameter γ (i.e., “*constant*” in the name), leading to communities such that the link density between the communities (external density) is lower than γ and the link density within communities (internal density) is more than γ . We set 6×10^{-3} as the resolution parameter in the case of all networks, i.e., aggregate data and scientific fields. We chose this parameter after exploration of the number of communities detected in contrast to the number of organizations and publications included in each bipartite community to prevent having too large or too small communities or an extremely high number of communities which will not be interpretable.

Results

Table 2 presents descriptive information about the co-authorship networks constructed using non-disambiguated and disambiguated data from iDiv and HJL cities. The lower number of connected components and decrease in the number of organizations in the disambiguated version of the networks show that in the non-disambiguated data there were multiple representations of the same institution that needed to be resolved before further analysis.

Note that the disambiguation results differ slightly between the two cases and the overlap from the iDiv sample to HJL cities is 828 publications (90%), which is due to non-matching DOIs. Note also that we excluded publications for which one or some of co-authoring organizations were not successfully disambiguated, which increases the quality and reliability of our data but decreases our coverage. Table 3 shows the networks constructed for each scientific field with iDiv and HJL cities data after disambiguation, which shows the highest share of publications were in Natural Sciences (NS). Ninety-three per cent of iDiv’s publications were categorized as NS, which aligns with the centre’s primary focus in this field.

Table 2: HJL organizations co-authorship networks using non-disambiguated and disambiguated data (G = giant component, Scopus 1996-2018)

Metrics	Non-disambiguated iDiv	Disambiguated iDiv	Non-disambiguated HJL cities	Disambiguated HJL cities
N. of connected components	228	1	61,906	22
N. of bipartite nodes	14,577	1,604	617,248	86,233
N. of bipartite edges	16,485	4,312	631,291	168,078
% of bipartite nodes in G	87	100	55	100
% of bipartite edges in G	90	100	65	100
N. of organizations	12,828	686	462,426	6,289
N. of organizations in G	11,243	686	264,938	6,268
N. of publications	1,749	918	154,822	79,944
N. of publications in G	1,462	918	75,055	79,894

³¹<https://github.com/vtraag/leidenalg>

Table 3: HJL organizations co-authorship networks in different OECD scientific fields (G = giant component, Agricultural Sciences (AS), Engineering Technology (ET), Natural Sciences (NS), Medical and Health Sciences (MHS), Humanities (H) and Social Sciences (SS))

Metrics	AS iDiv	AS HJL	ET iDiv	ET HJL	H iDiv	H HJL	MHS iDiv	MHS HJL	NS iDiv	NS HJL	SS iDiv	SS HJL
N. of connected components	4	8	1	18	1	18	4	17	1	17	1	19
N. of bipartite nodes	505	7,881	68	19,511	6	2,993	316	31,317	1,511	60,682	144	9,842
N. of bipartite edges	1,026	14,279	87	34,578	5	4,080	578	55,259	3,966	122,102	216	15,880
% of bipartite nodes in G	98	100	100	100	100	98	98	100	100	100	100	99
% of bipartite edges in G	99	100	100	100	100	99	99	100	100	100	100	100
N. of organizations	279	1,816	51	2,469	5	687	167	3,357	655	5,316	95	1,646
N. of organizations in G	270	1,809	51	2,449	5	669	163	3,341	655	5,300	95	1,623
N. of publications	226	6,065	17	17,042	1	2,306	149	27,960	856	55,366	49	8,196
N. of publications in G	223	6,055	17	17,008	1	2,279	146	27,935	856	55,337	49	8,158

Figure 2 presents a temporal comparison between scientific fields on the one hand and publications presented on iDiv website (top) and HJL cities (bottom) on the other hand. Humanities and Social Sciences (which are green and red lines at the bottom) have sharply increased, which is the case for all Germany previously presented in Stahlschmidt et al. (2019) and similar to the case of Berlin region presented in Akbaritabar (2021). It has to do with both an actual increase in publications, and increase in Scopus's coverage. For most fields, the gap between the two lines with the same colour (i.e., raw and fractional counts) are stable (**RQ1-2**).

Figure 2: Raw and fractional count of HJL publications by OECD fields (top, iDiv, bottom, HJL cities, 1996-2018, Scopus, fractional count based on organizations, AS: Agricultural Sciences, ET: Engineering Technology, NS: Natural Sciences, MHS: Medical and Health Sciences, H: Humanities and SS: Social Sciences)

Figure 3 presents the level of internationalization of collaborations (**RQ1-2**). iDiv (shown in the uppermost part on the right) is a highly exceptional case in that from 2013 it starts with about 50% international publications and arrives at about 75% in 2018. The trends of the HJL cities (other panels on left and bottom, i.e., “cities”) show the prevalence of intra-Germany collaborations have decreased in the most recent years. Conversely, international collaboration has increased in all fields, with AS, NS, and to a lesser extent ET, holding the highest rates of internationalization, although these are still below 50% in most years.

Figure 3: Share of intra-Germany versus multiple country co-authorship, top row, aggregate in HJL cities and iDiv, bottom rows, different fields for HJL cities data (1996-2018, Scopus), AS: Agricultural Sciences, ET: Engineering Technology, NS: Natural Sciences, MHS: Medical and Health Sciences, H: Humanities and SS: Social Sciences

Figure 4 presents a macro picture of the sectoral diversity (RQ3) of the institutions collaborating with HJL cities or iDiv. In some countries (e.g. the more industrially developed and western ones indicated with darker colours) there are representatives from all sectors active in research and publishing. Education (e.g., universities) and facility (e.g. Max Planck society institutes or Leibniz society institutes) were the most represented sectors. There was an interesting difference between iDiv’s collaborators worldwide and the picture from all institutions in the HJL cities. For example, while in education and facility, the trend of iDiv’s collaborations was similar to HJL region, regarding companies (e.g. business sector) and healthcare, it is highly different from the HJL region and shows the specific sectoral focus of iDiv, as the new organizational form. Table 4 presents the five countries with most organisations in each sector, further highlighting the differences between the iDiv and HJL cities datasets and the

dominance of education and facility organisations in research activity. The USA and China are the only collaborators among these five located outside Europe.

Figure 4: Countries worldwide collaborating with HJL *cities* or iDiv by sector (colour: N. of organizations. If a country does not have presence in a sector, it is shown with grey colour)

Table 4: Five countries with the highest number of organizations by sector (GRID data merged with Scopus 1996-2018)

Organization sector	Country code	Count iDiv	Count HJL Cities
Archive	DEU	4	26
	USA	8	22
	GBR	2	7
	CHN	1	4
	ESP	1	2
Company	DEU		132
	USA	1	70
	GBR	2	13
	ESP		3
	CHN		1
Education	USA	89	394
	CHN	35	213
	DEU	63	206
	GBR	28	111
	ESP	13	58

Organization sector	Country code	Count iDiv	Count HJL Cities
Facility	DEU	37	352
	USA	7	91
	CHN	7	74
	ESP	5	65
	GBR	4	43
Government	DEU	2	50
	USA	4	46
	CHN	4	14
	GBR		13
	ESP	1	11
Healthcare	DEU	1	263
	USA		105
	GBR		56
	CHN		26
	ESP		15
Non-profit	USA	5	83
	DEU	4	68
	GBR	4	18
	ESP	1	11
	CHN		6
Other	DEU	2	59
	USA	3	17
	ESP	2	13
	GBR	1	9
	CHN		1

Figure 5 presents the communities identified from the giant component of iDiv and HJL cities (RQ3-5). In the case of HJL cities, it presents scientific fields separately. Note that in both cases, all Unibund and iDiv members are part of the giant component which is connected in itself. But some institutions formed additional collaboration ties with one another, leading to denser areas inside the giant component. Our first aim was to identify these denser areas and the underlying factors behind these higher densities and groupings. Each dot or shape shows one community including multiple institutions. The count of institutions in each community is indicated on the X axis which has a log scale. The Y axis shows the aggregate number of publications by those institutions in a community on a log scale. The grey circles show communities which did not contain an Unibund or iDiv member. If a community includes only Unibund members, it is indicated with a *green plus*, and if it includes only iDiv members, a *blue square* is used. When the iDiv centre itself is in a given community, the colour is set to *black*. When a community includes a combination of iDiv and Unibund members, colour is set to *red* and shape is set to *triangle*. Therefore, if high cohesiveness exists, we expect to see a black triangle.

In the case of iDiv publications, shown in the uppermost right-hand panel, except for three communities with iDiv members (i.e., blue squares), all other institutions (i.e., iDiv centre itself, Unibund and iDiv members) are located in the most prolific community, which indicates a high cohesion in collaborations. When the larger context of the HJL cities is considered (i.e., cities), which still includes iDiv and Unibund members but they are placed in the regional context along with other institutions and their collaborators worldwide, then the identified denser areas of the giant component are further apart from each other. This is presented in the aggregate of cities in the uppermost left-hand panel where there are two green pluses with Unibund members, a triangle with an Unibund member and one iDiv member, versus multiple communities with iDiv members.

We present the variation among scientific fields only in the case of the HJL cities, since for iDiv, only a small number of publications (7%) were assigned to fields other than NS. The structure of collaborations is closest between HJL cities and iDiv, only in the case of NS which is the main field of publication for iDiv and to a lesser extent in AS. But, even in NS there are

six separate communities with iDiv members and iDiv centre is located in a community with two Unibund members. In all other fields, Unibund and iDiv members are located in separate communities, which indicates a lower cohesive collaboration structure in contrast to iDiv data. This can point to the disciplinary strength and scientific focus of these institutions which leads to the formation of a distinct group of regional, national or global collaborators that extends beyond the coalition agreements in the framework of Unibund or iDiv as these institutions (e.g., Max Planck Society members or Leibniz Association members are institutions with high level of international collaborations).

Figure 5: Organizations/publications of communities (black: includes iDiv centre, red/triangle: includes Unibund and iDiv members, blue/square: includes only iDiv member(s), green/plus: includes only Unibund members, grey/circle: others, cities: HJL cities, AS: Agricultural Sciences, ET: Engineering Technology, NS: Natural Sciences, MHS: Medical and Health Sciences, H: Humanities and SS: Social Sciences)

Table 5 presents more detail on the communities (**RQ3-5**) that include Unibund and/or iDiv members. It highlights the diversity of community members based on the percentage share of geographical regions and sectors. In geographical regions, we differentiate between HJL cities, Berlin, Germany and Europe to differentiate local, national, continent based or global collaborations. In case of iDiv publications, community 0³² has 77 member institutions, includes all Unibund and five of iDiv members, plus the iDiv centre itself. It also shows a high rate of geographical diversity with members coming from all regions. But, in the larger context (e.g., HJL cities), iDiv is located in community 3 with only one other iDiv member. The geographical composition of this community is mainly focused on Germany, Europe and HJL cities with only 4% of members from Oceania which is a highly different composition in contrast to community 0 in the iDiv data. Other iDiv and Unibund members are located in separate communities. While communities with Unibund members are less geographically diverse and mainly focused in Germany and Europe, communities with iDiv members have more international members. In terms of sectors, the majority of the community members are composed of education and facility. Government institutions are present only in communities with iDiv members. Health-care and non-profits are present in only a few of the communities. In the scientific fields, on the one hand, in most cases communities including Unibund members are composed of local and European institutions. Exceptions include four out of 17 communities i.e. community 1 in AS, community 0 in ET, community 1 in NS and community 3 in H where Unibund members have collaborated with institutions from other geographical regions. On the other hand, all of the communities with iDiv members are composed of international and global institutions. Communities where iDiv centre is located (see rows with bold font) follow the latter rule, but to a lesser extent.

Discussion and conclusions

This paper quantitatively explored the structure of institutional scientific collaborations in a geographical region in the central Germany comprised of three cities, Halle (Saale), Jena, and Leipzig (HJL cities) with a specific focus on the field of biodiversity and the German Centre for Integrative Biodiversity Research (iDiv) and its collaborators. The three universities of HJL cities joined forces to form a strategic coalition, i.e., Unibund, that has lasted 25 years. In addition, HJL is an interesting region since it does not comply with the idea of a centralized and concentrated metropolitan area (Abbasiharofteh & Broekel, 2020; Akbaritabar, 2021; Balland et al., 2020). From 2012, Unibund coalition, in collaboration with Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research (UFZ) and seven other non-university institutions has established a new organizational entity, the German Centre for Integrative Biodiversity Research (iDiv).

Our main intention was to explore how Unibund members have collaborated with each other and to what extent iDiv as the new organizational form has integrated its diverse group of members into the collaboration network. In addition, we compared the structure of scientific collaborations based on the self-represented scientific output of iDiv on their website with the larger context of scientific output of the HJL region.

In methodological terms, we presented the effect of disambiguation of organization names on results. We showed that disambiguation is crucial if we intend to construct networks and investigate collaboration trajectories (Donner et al., 2019; Rimmert, 2018; Rimmert et al., 2017; Tekles & Bornmann, 2020; Wu & Ding, 2013). An attempt at doing so without proper disambiguation would be erroneous (Akbaritabar, 2021)).

³²These numbers are only labels used for community names and do not have a numeric meaning.

Moreover, the German science system in general (Stahlschmidt et al., 2019; Stephen et al., 2020) and HJL region specifically, present an increasing trend of fractional counts of publications versus raw counts indicating increased institutional co-authorship. We observe that most co-authorship occurs within Germany and only a few fields (e.g., NS -where iDiv is mostly active- and AS and to a lesser extent ET) show higher rates of multiple country co-authorship which is similar to Akbaritabar (2021)'s findings of the Berlin metropolitan region. Note that this is in line with the focus of natural versus social sciences, where natural sciences share resources over large, global teams to manage costs and work on globally relevant research questions (Chompalov et al., 2002; Shrum et al., 2001, 2007), whereas more social sciences and humanities work focuses on regional/local questions and is conducted by smaller teams (Akbaritabar et al., 2020; Leahey, 2016). However, exceptional cases might exist to these disciplinary traditions. These disciplinary traditions affect collaboration practices as well and, in some fields, co-authorship with multiple institutions and nations prevail (e.g., particle physics) and in other fields (e.g., humanities) publications with smaller number of authors is the norm.

Research activity in many countries is still dominated by the education sector (or in rare cases such as Germany, facility and education dominate the picture) and other sectors have a smaller share in publications. More is still needed to be done for university-industry relations and companies (as representative of business sector) have only marginal positions in a few small and less prolific clusters and their collaboration is limited to specific fields (e.g., AS, ET and NS). This might be affected by Scopus indexed publications (Baas et al., 2020).

Regarding the main aims of our paper, we found that Unibund coalition operated as a top-down policy inspiring further scientific collaboration. But in practice, while its members collaborate in the framework of the coalition, they maintain a more cohesive and distinctive group of collaborators distributed nationally or in Europe. iDiv was established as an interdisciplinary network. Based on their self-represented scientific output, it has integrated a diverse group of institutions as members. Furthermore, it has established international and global collaboration ties. Once we compared the structure of collaborations *within* and *between* Unibund and iDiv members and scientific output of the larger context of HJL region, we observed that the highly cohesive structure based on iDiv's publications was more the exception than the rule. Even though all three of Unibund and five of iDiv members were cohesively collaborating with each other in the community 0 based on publications extracted from iDiv, based on the HJL cities' publications, only one iDiv member is located in the community 3 with iDiv centre and other members are located in separate cohesive communities with a more (in case of iDiv members) or less (in case of Unibund members) international composition. iDiv members' collaboration with each other (i.e., the network constructed based on iDiv data) is only a small part of the bigger collaboration trajectory. A larger share of their collaboration is still composed of working with a global group of other collaborators. This could inform future policies in designing further collaborations among the coalition members.

To conclude, although an *Integrated European Research Area* (Hoekman et al., 2010) has formed, nevertheless, geographical proximity (Balland et al., 2020; Rammer et al., 2020) is not enough to ensure regional cooperation (Abbasiharofteh & Broekel, 2020) similar to top-down policies (Akbaritabar, 2021). Furthermore, even use of *bureaucracy* and establishment of new organizational entities (Shrum et al., 2007, pp. 192, 200–201) do not ensure a cohesive collaboration structure. Unibund and iDiv have been successful (e.g., in terms of number of publications) mainly in the natural sciences to shape the structure of scientific collaborations in the HJL region. Still, in other scientific fields, where these institutions are actively publishing,

a less cohesive collaboration structure is formed and there is space for these strategic coalitions to explore unrealized potentials. Nevertheless, it is necessary to note that international scientific collaboration is not always necessary for instance in case of niche topics focused on local problems and this could well be the reason some fields have a more locally oriented network of collaborators.

The main limitation of our paper is the coverage of organization name disambiguation and being limited to only Scopus indexed content for scientific output (Baas et al., 2020). This does not include other modes of scientific collaboration that institutions might carry out such as sharing infrastructure and resources, to name a few (Chompalov et al., 2002; Shrum et al., 2001, 2007). Our analysis is limited to the level of scientific organization and more detailed investigation in individual scientists' level, which requires fine-grained author name disambiguation techniques, would reveal more reliable insight into the structure of scientific collaborations and how specific individuals influence it.

We modeled the networks as a bipartite one which is an improvement to the one-mode projection of it (Akbaritabar & Barbato, 2021). But the number of available algorithms to identify communities in this type of network is still limited. Nevertheless, there are recent developments in the area of bipartite community detection and future work could evaluate robustness of community detection results, using new algorithms such as *BiMLPA* (Taguchi et al., 2020) with the standard implementation of it in CDlib library (Rossetti et al., 2019) that allows for comparative analysis of community detection results. This will further ensure that the structure we are observing is robust to multiple community detection methods and is the result of the scientific collaborations in the region.

Table 5: Composition of the communities including Unibund and/or iDiv members by region and sector in aggregate and by fields (N = community size, P = aggregate publications, iDiv = Y; includes iDiv centre, I = number of iDiv members, I = number of Unibund members)

Data	Region (%)										Sector (%)												
	clus ter	N	P	iD iv	I	U	Afri ca	Ameri cas	Asia	Ber lin	DE	Eur ope	HJ L citi es	Ocea nia	No regi on	Arch ive	Comp any	Educa tion	Facil ity	Govern ment	Health care	No n- pro fit	Oth er
Aggre gate cities	0	5	24,6 16		1					20	20	60						60	20		20		
	1	1	29,6 08		1						25	17	50	8				42	42		17		
	2	9	20,1 27		1						67		33					67	33				
	3	2	11,4 81	Y	1						48	36	12	4				72	20	4		4	
	4	2	4,74 4		1			42			8	46	4					79	17	4			
	7	1	2,39 3		1			31	15			46	8					62	31	8			
	9	2	1,91 2		1		5	14			27	50	5					27	45	14		9	5
	25	1	569		1		6	6	12		44	31					6	56	19	6	12		
	108	1	208		1		7				27	40						47	33	7		7	7
	164	1	109		1			6	6		12	76				18	6	29	35	6			6
Aggre gate iDiv	0	7	3,06 1	Y	5	3	3	5	9	4	38	29	10	3		1		70	22	3		3	1
	2	2	71		1		4		15		22	59				7		63	7	22			
	4	1	60		1		33	17			11	33	6			6	6	50	11	6		11	11
	42	2	3		1						10 0								100				
AS cities	0	1	2,29 8	Y	1			8		17	33	25	17				67	8	8	8		8	
	1	1	2,08 6		2	1	18				71		12				59	35	6				
	2	1	1,36 3		1			8			54		38				62	15	15	8			
	3	2	1,32 5		1			11	4	4	48	19	11	4			67	30				4	
4	2	903		1			39	4	7	7	39	4					71	18	7		4		

Data	Region (%)						Sector (%)																		
	clus-ter	N	P	iD	I	U	Afri-ca	Ameri-cas	Asi-a	Ber-lin	DE	Eur-ope	HJ	Ocea-nia	No	regi-on	Arch-ive	Comp-any	Educa-tion	Facil-ity	Govern-ment	Health-care	No-n-pro-fit	Oth-er	
	5	29	426		1		3	31	17		17	28	3					3	62	28	3			3	
	7	40	271		1		25	10	12	5	40	8						2	52	28	2	2	10	2	
	72	13	31		1			38	8	15	38				8				38	31	15		8		
	343	1	1		1					100										100					
ET cities	0	19	9,540			1		5	5	42	11	32	5				11	42	37			11			
	1	13	5,773		1				8	54	23	15							54	38			8		
	2	14	4,664		1					50	29	21							64	21	7	7			
	3	15	1,420		1				7	47	20	20							53	33	7		7		
	10	26	200		1		4	27	4	4	58	4						4	69	15	4	4	4		
	32	8	89		1				25		62	12							62	38					
	82	1	46		1		9	18	36	9	18	9					9		73	18					
	101	9	58	Y					44	11	33	11							67	22	11				
	103	1	57		1			38	25		25	6	6						56	38	6				
	131	8	30		1			50	25	25								12	50	12	12	12			
NS cities	0	23	37,7	Y	1	2			9	57	9	26							78	22					
	1	1	21,8			1		7	7	29	14	36	7							36					
	3	1	2,785		1			37		11	47	5							79	21					
	4	1	2,195		1		7	13	20	13	33	7	7						60	40					
	7	2	1,694		1		5	23		14	45	5	9					5	32	36	18		5	5	
	8	1	1,253		2		13	33		33	13	7							40	53			7		
	29	1	384		1				10	70	20				10			20	40	10		10	10		
	103	1	105		1			8	38	15	38								62	23	8	8			

Data	Region (%)						Sector (%)																	
	clus ter	N	P	iD iv	I	U	Afri ca	Ameri cas	As ia	Ber lin	DE U	Eur ope	HJ L citi es	Ocea nia	No regi on	Arch ive	Comp any	Educa tion	Facil ity	Govern ment	Health care	No n- pro fit	Oth er	
MHS cities	0	8	11,9 01			1					62	12	25					75			25			
	1	1	10,1 04			1				55			45					55	18		27			
	2	6	6,03 8			1				67			33					67			33			
	4	2 3	1,72 4	Y	1			4		39	43	13					4	61	22		4	9		
	5	1 8	862		1		6	22	28			33	6	6				67	17	11			6	
	6	2 4	894		1			58	8	4	25	4						75	21				4	
	8	3 5	429		2		6	34	20	3	11	23	3			3		57	34		6			
	31	2 1	167		1			57	14		10	14	5					62	24	14				
	139	8 3	37		1			12	12		12	62				12		50	25	12				
	247	3 0	5		1				67		33					33		67						
H cities	0	3	707		1					33	33	33						67	33					
	1	5	468		1				20	60		20						80		20				
	2	2 9	657		1		3	34		7	41	3	7				3	90	7					
	3	6	337		1				17	50	17	17						100						
	7	1 6	77		1			6		6	44	25	12			19		56	19				6	
	13	8	45		1		12		12		50	25						62	38					
	47	4 5	5	Y							75	25	25					25	50	25				
	64	1	2		1								10	0					100					
	SS cities	0	5	2,46 5		1					40	20	40						60			40		
		1	9	1,78 7		1					78	11	11						100					
2		6	1,58 0		1					67		33				17		83						
3		2 7	1,19 7		1		4	37	4	7	41	4	4			7		85	7					
5		1 8	843	Y	1			6		11	44	17	17	6				61	22			11	6	
26		2 4	72		1			58	4		33	4						62	21	4	12			

Data	Region (%)						Sector (%)																
	clus ter	N	P	iD iv	I	U	Afri ca	Ameri cas	As ia	Ber lin	DE U	Eur ope	HJ L citi es	Ocea nia	No regi on	Arch ive	Comp any	Educa tion	Facil ity	Govern ment	Health care	No n- pro fit	Oth er
	34	20	60		1			10	30		5	45	5	5				80	10	5	5		
	35	18	64		1		11	22	11	6	22	6	6	22		6		39	22	11	17	6	
	46	13	49		1		8	54	8	8	23					8		85		8			

Data Accessibility

Data cannot be made publicly available due to the licensing and contract terms of the original data. Python scripts to replicate the used organization name disambiguation technique and bipartite network construction and bipartite community detection could be publicly accessed under <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4657326>

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References

- Abbasiharofteh, M., & Broekel, T. (2020). Still in the shadow of the wall? The case of the Berlin biotechnology cluster. *Environment and Planning A: Economy and Space*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0308518X20933904>
- Akbaritabar, A. (2021). A quantitative view of the structure of institutional scientific collaborations using the example of Berlin. *Quantitative Science Studies*, 2(2), 753–777. https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00131
- Akbaritabar, A., & Barbato, G. (2021). An internationalised Europe and regionally focused Americas: A network analysis of higher education studies. *European Journal of Education*, 56(2), 219–234. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejed.12446>
- Akbaritabar, A., Traag, V. A., Caimo, A., & Squazzoni, F. (2020). Italian Sociologists: A Community of Disconnected Groups. *Scientometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-020-03555-w>
- Baas, J., Schotten, M., Plume, A., Côté, G., & Karimi, R. (2020). Scopus as a curated, high-quality bibliometric data source for academic research in quantitative science studies. *Quantitative Science Studies*, 1(1), 377–386. https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00019
- Balland, P.-A., Jara-Figueroa, C., Petralia, S. G., Steijn, M. P. A., Rigby, D. L., & Hidalgo, C. A. (2020). Complex economic activities concentrate in large cities. *Nature Human Behaviour*, 4(3), 248–254. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-019-0803-3>
- Boshoff, N. (2009). Neo-colonialism and research collaboration in Central Africa. *Scientometrics*, 81(2), 413. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-008-2211-8>
- Breiger, R. L. (1974). The Duality of Persons and Groups. *Social Forces*, 53(2), 181–190. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sf/53.2.181>
- Chompalov, I., Genuth, J., & Shrum, W. (2002). The organization of scientific collaborations. *Research Policy*, 31(5), 749–767.
- Craven, D., Winter, M., Hotzel, K., Gaikwad, J., Eisenhauer, N., Hohmuth, M., König-Ries, B., & Wirth, C. (2019). Evolution of interdisciplinarity in biodiversity science. *Ecology and Evolution*, 9(12), 6744–6755. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.5244>
- Donner, P., Rimmert, C., & van Eck, N. J. (2019). Comparing institutional-level bibliometric research performance indicator values based on different affiliation disambiguation systems. *Quantitative Science Studies*, 1(1), 150–170. https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00013
- Habel, J. C., Eggermont, H., Günter, S., Mulwa, R. K., Rieckmann, M., Koh, L. P., Niassy, S., Ferguson, J. W. H., Gebremichael, G., Githiru, M., Weisser, W. W., & Lens, L. (2014). Towards more equal footing in north–south biodiversity research: European and sub-Saharan viewpoints. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 23(12), 3143–3148. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-014-0761-z>
- Haelewaters, D., Hofmann, T. A., & Romero-Olivares, A. L. (2021). Ten simple rules for Global North researchers to stop perpetuating helicopter research in the Global South. *PLOS Computational Biology*, 17(8), e1009277. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1009277>

- Hoekman, J., Frenken, K., & Tijssen, R. J. W. (2010). Research collaboration at a distance: Changing spatial patterns of scientific collaboration within Europe. *Research Policy*, 39(5), 662–673. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2010.01.012>
- Katz, J. S., & Martin, B. R. (1997). What is research collaboration? *Research Policy*, 26(1), 1–18. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-7333\(96\)00917-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-7333(96)00917-1)
- Leahey, E. (2016). From Sole Investigator to Team Scientist: Trends in the Practice and Study of Research Collaboration. *Annual Review of Sociology*, 42(1), 81–100. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-soc-081715-074219>
- Newman, M. E. J. (2004). Detecting community structure in networks. *The European Physical Journal B - Condensed Matter*, 38(2), 321–330. <https://doi.org/10.1140/epjb/e2004-00124-y>
- OECD. (2007). *Revised Field of Science and Technology (FOS) classification in the Frascati Manual (Classification, Field of science and technology classification, FOS, Frascati, Methodology, Research and development)*. <https://www.oecd.org/science/inno/38235147.pdf>
- Rammer, C., Kinne, J., & Blind, K. (2020). Knowledge proximity and firm innovation: A microgeographic analysis for Berlin. *Urban Studies*, 57(5), 996–1014. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0042098018820241>
- Reichardt, J., & Bornholdt, S. (2004). Detecting fuzzy community structures in complex networks with a Potts model. *Physical Review Letters*, 93(21), 218701. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.93.218701>
- Rimmert, C. (2018). *Institutional disambiguation for further countries—An exploration with extensive use of wikidata (project report)*. [Report]. Bielefeld University, Institute for Interdisciplinary Studies of Science (I²SoS). <https://pub.uni-bielefeld.de/record/2930347#APA>
- Rimmert, C., Schwechheimer, H., & Winterhager, M. (2017). *Disambiguation of author addresses in bibliometric databases—Technical report*. [Report]. <https://pub.uni-bielefeld.de/record/2914944>
- Rossetti, G., Milli, L., & Cazabet, R. (2019). CDLIB: A python library to extract, compare and evaluate communities from complex networks. *Applied Network Science*, 4(1), 52. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41109-019-0165-9>
- Shrum, W., Chompalov, I., & Genuth, J. (2001). Trust, Conflict and Performance in Scientific Collaborations. *Social Studies of Science*, 31(5), 681–730. <https://doi.org/10.1177/030631201031005002>
- Shrum, W., Genuth, J., Carlson, W. B., Chompalov, I., & Bijker, W. E. (2007). *Structures of Scientific Collaboration*. MIT Press.
- Stahlschmidt, S., Stephen, D., & Hinze, S. (2019). *Performance and Structures of the German Science System* (EFI, p. 91). Studien zum deutschen Innovationssystem. https://www.e-fi.de/fileadmin/Assets/Studien/2019/StuDIS_05_2019.pdf
- Stephen, D., Stahlschmidt, S., & Hinze, S. (2020). *Performance and Structures of the German Science System 2020* (EFI). Studien zum deutschen Innovationssystem. https://www.e-fi.de/fileadmin/Assets/Studien/2020/StuDIS_05_2020.pdf
- Taguchi, H., Murata, T., & Liu, X. (2020). BiMLPA: Community Detection in Bipartite Networks by Multi-Label Propagation. In N. Masuda, K.-I. Goh, T. Jia, J. Yamanoi, & H. Sayama (Eds.), *Proceedings of NetSci-X 2020: Sixth International Winter School and Conference on Network Science* (pp. 17–31). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-38965-9_2
- Tekles, A., & Bornmann, L. (2020). Author name disambiguation of bibliometric data: A comparison of several unsupervised approaches. *Quantitative Science Studies*, 1–38. https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00081
- Traag, V. A., Van Dooren, P., & Nesterov, Y. (2011). Narrow scope for resolution-limit-free community detection. *Physical Review E*, 84(1), 016114. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevE.84.016114>
- Traag, V. A., Waltman, L., & van Eck, N. J. (2019). From Louvain to Leiden: Guaranteeing well-connected communities. *Scientific Reports*, 9(1), 5233. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-41695-z>
- Tydecks, L., Jeschke, J. M., Wolf, M., Singer, G., & Tockner, K. (2018). Spatial and topical imbalances in biodiversity research. *PLOS ONE*, 13(7), e0199327. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0199327>

Wu, J., & Ding, X.-H. (2013). Author name disambiguation in scientific collaboration and mobility cases. *Scientometrics*, 96(3), 683–697. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-013-0978-8>